

D4.1 ARCHITECTURE AND SERVICES SPECIFICATIONS REPORT

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Lead Beneficiary	DRAXIS			
Responsible Author	Petros Gasteratos (DRAXIS)			
Contributions from	Agathoklis Dimitrakos (AgroApps), Maria Banti (AgroApps), Panos Ilias (EV ILVO), Bert Callens (EV ILVO), Iason Tsardanidis (NOA), Thanassis Drivas (NOA), Alexia Tsouni (NOA), Stella Girtsou (NOA)			

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Full term
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
AOI	Area Of Interest
AVIST	Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series
BFAST	Breaks For Additive Season and Trend
BOA	Bottom-Of-Atmosphere
BSM	Burnt Scar Mapping
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CC	Cross-Compliance
CCTM	Cultivated Crop type Maps
Chl	Chlorophyll content
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
cGANs	Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks
CNNs	Convolutional Neural Networks
DFS	Data Fusion Service
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
EFA	Ecological Focus Area
EO	Earth Observation
FAPAR	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation
fCover	Fraction of Vegetation Cover
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GEE	Google Earth Engine
GIS	Geographical Information System
GMED	Grassland Mowing Events Detection Service
gml	Geography Markup Language
GRD	Ground Range Detected
GRU	Gated Recurrent Units
GSAA	Geo Spatial Aid Application
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
InSAR	Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar
json	JavaScript Object Notation
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification System
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MVP	Minimum Value Product
ML	Machine Learning
MSI	Multispectral Instrument

MVT	Model-View-Template
NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
NIR	Near Infrared
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
NVZ	Nitrate Vulnerable Zone
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OTSC	On-The-Spot-Check
PA	Paying Agency
ReCAP	Reinforcing CAP
RESTful API	Representational state transfer Application Programming Interface
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
RON	Relative Orbit Number
RS	Remote Sensing
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Index Equation
S1	Sentinel-1
S2	Sentinel-2
SAVI	Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SCL	Scene Classification Map
SD	Standard deviation
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SEN4CAP	The Sentinels for Common Agricultural Policy
SLC	Single Look Complex
SMR	Statuary Management Requirements
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SOA	Service-oriented Architecture
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SOC	Soil Organic Carbo
SWIR	Short-wave infrared
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TOC	Top of Canopy
TMS	Tile map service
UAT	User Acceptance Testing
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
US	User Stories
USLE	Universal Soil Index Equation
VH	vertical transmit, horizontal receive
VI	Vegetation Index
VV	vertical transmit, vertical receive

WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service
WMS	Web Map Service

Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to define the system architecture, the software and hardware requirements, the integration of the various components as well as the services specifications.

This deliverable is based on the Deliverable 2.2 Report of customer requirements from ENVISION services which contributed to the specification of the main points of the current deliverable and acts as the basis for its development.

This document defines the set of techniques and technologies that they are considered to be the most appropriate in order to produce the system architecture and design as well as provides the specifications (data, visualisation) of the services that will be developed during the project. Specifically, the sections of this deliverable are:

Section 1 – ENVISION Architecture: Contains a description of the ENVISION architecture, the design inputs, the system components, the dataflow diagram and the system monitoring and security.

Section 2 – ENVISION Services Specifications: Contains a description of each service that have been developed including the internal and external dependencies as well as dependencies from other services.

Section 3 – ENVISION’s development pipeline: Contains the software development methodology that has been used during the development of the project.

Section 4 – Conclusions: Contains the main conclusions of this deliverable.

1 ENVISION Architecture

1.1 System Overview

The following diagram provides a high-level overview of the ENVISION system’s architecture and the arrows indicate the flow of communication and data transfer between different components.

Figure 1: ENVISION System Architecture

- ❑ **User interface:** This represents the user-facing component built using Vue.js and Vuetify. It communicates directly with the Backend Logic Layer to provide functionalities and services to the users.
- ❑ **Backend Logic Layer:** A centralized backend component that integrates with multiple databases. It processes user queries and requests and communicates with the frontend and Data Storage components.
- ❑ **Data Storage:** This represents the storage layer using PostgreSQL with the PostGIS extension, which handles spatial data and other related functionalities.
- ❑ **Data Visualisation:** Represents the component using Apache ECharts for creating interactive charts and graphs based on the data provided.
- ❑ **Geospatial Visualisation:** A specialized component for visualizing geospatial data, leveraging Mapbox GL JS and OpenLayers libraries.
- ❑ **Security:** This component ensures the security of user data and system interactions, handling encryption, and user authentication and authorization.
- ❑ **Scalability:** Represents the infrastructure scalability component of the platform. Docker containerization is used to ensure efficient deployment and scaling.

1.1.1 Purpose of the ENVISION System

The agriculture sector, both from a governmental oversight perspective and from a farmer's viewpoint, requires continuous and systematic monitoring. Traditional methods of monitoring have been fragmented, focusing on specific fields and dates. ENVISION aims to revolutionize this approach by shifting the focus from isolated monitoring to territory-wide and year-round observation.

1.1.2 Key objectives

The primary objectives of ENVISION include its comprehensive monitoring capabilities. It offers stakeholders an all-encompassing view of agricultural land, enabling them to make informed decisions based on provided insights. But the system's effectiveness doesn't stop at mere observation. ENVISION harnesses the vast datasets available from sources like GEOSS, Copernicus, and DIAS. Synergising these datasets allows for the development of insightful data products.

Another defining attribute of ENVISION is its commitment to automation and scalability. The agricultural sector is vast and ever-evolving. Thus, solutions that are static or require constant manual intervention can quickly become obsolete. ENVISION, with its integration of advanced technologies and methodologies, provides automated, cutting-edge solutions that can readily scale up or down based on the needs of the hour.

1.1.3 Data products

Speaking of the value that ENVISION brings to the table, no one can overlook its diverse range of data products and services. The system transforms raw, often overwhelming data into actionable and comprehensible insights. For instance, one of the data products, "Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series", is integral for the Lithuanian PA NPA and is driven by user requirements such as UR5/UR7/UR13/UR16/UR17/UR18. This product is complemented by services like "Harvest events detection", offered by the service provider NOA (more information is provided in the table in Chapter 2). These offerings reflect the versatility of ENVISION, addressing varied needs ranging from vegetation analysis and soil health to specific requirements for different business cases. Such range in data products and services ensures that stakeholders across the spectrum, be it in crop management, conservation, or market strategy, find value in the ENVISION system.

1.1.4 Technology Stack

At its core, ENVISION is a technological marvel. It seamlessly integrates various technologies to deliver its promise. From gathering data using satellite imagery and historical records to processing this data using cutting-edge algorithms and machine learning, the system can assist the daily needs and requirements of the PAs. The fusion of multi-source and multi-temporal data ensures a holistic view of the agricultural landscape. And to make all this technological effectiveness accessible, ENVISION boasts a user-friendly interface, developed with Vue.js and Vuetify. This interface acts as a bridge, allowing users to interact effortlessly with the system's different services and functionalities.

1.1.5 Customer-Centric Development

ENVISION's design and development have been in close interaction with its customers. This ensures that the system is not only technologically advanced but also aligned with the actual needs of the end-users.

1.1.6 User Interface

In the digital age, the interface of a system often serves as its first impression. A well-designed, user-friendly interface can greatly enhance user experience and engagement, ensuring that even the most technologically advanced systems remain accessible and intuitive to its users. Recognizing this, ENVISION has prioritized the development of a user-centric interface that not only looks appealing but is also intuitive to navigate and interact with.

Central to this endeavor is the choice of the Vue.js framework. Vue.js, known for its progressive nature, allows for the building of more testable and maintainable user interfaces. It offers a blend of established conventions with the flexibility of crafting custom solutions, enabling developers to create seamless user experiences. As a framework, Vue.js has gained popularity because of its adaptability; it can be as simple or as complex as needed, making it an ideal choice for projects that might scale or evolve over time.

Complementing Vue.js is Vuetify, a material design component framework. Vuetify brings a rich set of pre-made components and features, ensuring that the ENVISION interface is not only functional but also quite attractive. Material design, with its principles of light, surface, and movement, ensures that the user interface has a modern feel, with intuitive visual transitions. The combination of Vue.js and Vuetify means that the frontend is both robust and responsive, adapting easily to various screen sizes and devices.

Delving deeper into the interface itself, users are welcomed with an overview screen that provides a snapshot of the system's capabilities. This general overview is designed to be straightforward, presenting users with the most essential information at a glance. As they navigate further, detailed screens offer in-depth insights into specific parcels and other relevant data. The consistent design across different screens ensures that users, once familiar with the interface's layout, can navigate and utilize its functionalities with ease. Each business case, while having the same foundational screens, offers unique visualizations and services specific to the data and requirements defined in the Description of Action (DoA). More detailed information and screens of the ENVISION platform are presented in the respective deliverables (D4.3 and D4.4).

1.1.7 Backend Logic Layer

The backbone of any digital system lies in its backend infrastructure, something that also applies to ENVISION. While the frontend serves as the face of the system, the backend logic layer acts as its brain, ensuring seamless data management, processing, and delivery.

At the heart of ENVISION's technological infrastructure is its centralized backend. This centralized approach ensures that data from various sources, be it satellite imagery or agricultural metrics, are aggregated and managed in a cohesive manner. Such a unified system not only streamlines data processing but also ensures data integrity and consistency. By eliminating data silos and ensuring that every piece of information is processed and stored centrally, ENVISION guarantees that users receive accurate and up-to-date insights, regardless of the data's origin.

Integration with multiple databases is a critical aspect of this backend. Agriculture, by its very nature, encompasses a vast array of data types, from geospatial coordinates of land parcels to historical in-situ data. To manage this diverse data spectrum, ENVISION's backend interfaces with a variety of databases, each tailored for specific data types and structures. This multi-database approach ensures that data retrieval is optimized, and storage solutions are tailored to the nature of the data, be it spatial data requiring PostGIS extensions or standard relational data in PostgreSQL.

Beyond mere data storage, the backend's true value emerges in its role in processing user queries and requests. When a user interacts with the ENVISION platform, be it a simple data retrieval request or a more complex query like distinguishing between organic and conventional farming parcels, it's the backend that does the heavy lifting. Through algorithms, machine learning models, and data processing pipelines, the backend interprets the user's request, fetches and processes the relevant data, and then communicates the results back to the frontend. This dynamic ensures that users get accurate, timely, and relevant results.

The backend logic layer of ENVISION seamlessly blends complex data management with user-centric service delivery, ensuring that the platform remains robust, and reliable.

1.1.8 Data Storage

The ENVISION system, which handles a plethora of agricultural data types, having a robust and versatile data storage system is non-negotiable. Central to this infrastructure is the use of PostgreSQL, complemented by the PostGIS extension.

PostgreSQL stands out as one of the world's most advanced open-source relational database systems. It's renowned for its extensibility, reliability, and data integrity. What sets PostgreSQL apart is its ability to be both a powerful relational database and, with the right extensions, a NoSQL system, catering to diverse data needs. In the context of ENVISION, this flexibility ensures that varied data, from crop types to soil metrics, are stored efficiently and securely.

ENVISION's backend is equipped with search functionalities that allow users to query the system in versatile ways. Whether it's a simple search based on a parcel ID or a more complex query to identify misclassified plots, the system's data retrieval mechanisms ensure that users get the information they need, when they need it. By optimizing data indexing, leveraging PostgreSQL's powerful query capabilities, and ensuring that the system's architecture supports rapid data retrieval, ENVISION transforms raw data into actionable insights. Although the services are offered from three distinct providers, each drawing from varied data sources and infrastructures, ENVISION consolidates everything into a unified database. This synergetic architecture ensures users do not have to perform connections with multiple service providers. Instead, a single interface with the ENVISION platform suffices. However, for those who prefer direct access to a specific provider, dedicated APIs are available.

1.1.9 Data visualisation

In the vast landscape of agricultural data, where numbers and metrics are numerous, the ability to visualize this data becomes important. For ENVISION, data visualization isn't just an add-on; it's a fundamental pillar that transforms various data into tangible insights, providing users with a clear and immediate understanding of the information at hand.

The significance of data visualization in ENVISION can't be overstated. Agriculture is a domain where decisions often hinge on many differences. Whether it's the changes in soil quality over time or the spatial distribution of different crop types, visual representation ensures that these differences are immediately observable. Through charts, graphs, and maps, complex datasets are turned into visual formats that are intuitive and easy to interpret. This ensures that the end-users can make informed decisions quickly and effectively.

At the heart of ENVISION's data visualization effectiveness is the integration of Apache ECharts. ECharts, a powerful, interactive charting and visualization library, brings a wealth of functionalities tailored for diverse data representation needs. It offers a vast array of chart types, from basic line and bar charts to more complex visualizations like heat maps and scatter plots. But ECharts isn't just about variety; it's about interactivity. Users can zoom, pan, and drill down into charts, allowing them to explore data at both macro and micro levels. The library's ability to handle large datasets ensures that even the most comprehensive data, such as territory-wide agricultural metrics, can be visualized seamlessly without compromising performance.

Beyond its technical capabilities, ECharts also offers a great visualisation. With customizable themes and styles, data visualizations in ENVISION are not just informative but also visually appealing. This ensures that users are not just presented with data, but with insights that resonate, prompting informed actions and decisions.

By leveraging the capabilities of Apache ECharts, ENVISION ensures that every data point, no matter how intricate or voluminous, is presented in a manner that illuminates, educates, and empowers.

1.1.10 Geospatial Visualisation

The reliance on geospatial data is intrinsic to the agricultural sector; it provides the contextual framework within which all agricultural activities are planned and assessed. ENVISION acknowledges this reliance by integrating geospatial visualization at its core, transforming geographical data into interactive, informative maps that offer a real-world view of agricultural landscapes.

The data plays a pivotal role in land monitoring, allowing for the tracking of changes over time, whether they be the result of human activity or natural processes. By visualizing this data, ENVISION provides a spatial dimension to agricultural management, enabling PAs to see the full picture and make decisions that are grounded in the geographical reality of the Area of Interest.

To realize this vision, ENVISION harnesses the capabilities of two powerful libraries: Mapbox GL JS and OpenLayers. Mapbox GL JS is renowned for its high-performance rendering capabilities and its ability to produce rich, interactive maps. Its utilization of WebGL technology allows for smooth transitions and real-time manipulations, such as zooming and panning, even when dealing with large datasets. OpenLayers complements this by offering a wide range of features for adding overlays, rendering vector data, and integrating various map services. Together, these libraries provide a robust platform for ENVISION's geospatial visualization needs.

The features and functionalities offered by these libraries are extensive. Users can interact with the map in intuitive ways, selecting specific parcels of land to view detailed information or overlaying various data sets to understand the relationship between different geographical factors. They can visualize temporal changes through historical imagery layers or analyze spatial patterns, such as soil erosion or vegetation cover. Moreover, the system allows for the customization of map views, enabling

users to tailor the visualization to their specific needs, whether that's highlighting areas of interest or integrating third-party data for enhanced analysis.

1.1.11 Security Measures

In the digital landscape, where data is both currency and commodity, security is not a feature but a foundational necessity. The ENVISION system, which handles sensitive agricultural data, is acutely aware of this necessity. By prioritizing security, ENVISION ensures the integrity of user data and the trustworthiness of the interactions within the system, which is crucial for maintaining user confidence and upholding data privacy standards.

The importance of security within the ENVISION system cannot be understated. PAs entrust the system with detailed information about farmers' declarations. Recognizing this, ENVISION has adopted security protocols to safeguard this information. The system is not just protected against external threats but also secured from within, ensuring that data remains secure throughout its lifecycle — from entry to storage to retrieval.

Central to ENVISION's security strategy is the use of advanced data encryption techniques. Encryption acts as the first line of defense, transforming the raw data into a format that is unreadable to unauthorized entities. Whether data is at rest within the system's databases or in transit between server and client, encryption ensures that it remains confidential and secure. By employing encryption standards, ENVISION can provide assurance that even in the event of an interception, the data's integrity and confidentiality remain uncompromised.

ENVISION uses OAuth2 and Keycloak as user authentication and authorisation form. OAuth2, an industry-standard protocol for authorization, is employed within the system to manage access to user accounts and resources. Keycloak, an open-source identity and access management solution, works in tandem with OAuth2 to provide a robust authentication framework. Together, they ensure that only legitimate users can access the system and that they can only interact with the data and features that their credentials permit. This multi-layered approach to authentication and authorization not only prevents unauthorized access but also ensures that user interactions with the system are continuously monitored and managed.

1.1.12 Scalability

In an era where data volumes and computational demands grow exponentially, scalability is not just a beneficial feature but a critical requirement. ENVISION, with its expansive reach across agricultural land monitoring, is designed with this scalability at its core. The ability to scale ensures that as the system's user base expands and the volume of data swells, ENVISION can continue to provide seamless service without degradation in performance or user experience.

Scalability within ENVISION is twofold: It must manage an increasing entry of data from various sources and also accommodate a growing number of users accessing this data. The system is developed to handle these scaling demands gracefully, whether that means increasing to process more data during peak declaration season or expanding to new territories with additional data sets and user requirements. This adaptability is crucial for maintaining the system's reliability and effectiveness, regardless of load and complexity.

At the heart of ENVISION's scalability strategy is Docker. Docker containers encapsulate the system's applications, along with their environments, ensuring that they run consistently across any

infrastructure. This is particularly valuable for ENVISION, which must be agile and responsive to varying demands.

Docker's role in scalability is pivotal. By containerizing the system's applications, Docker allows ENVISION to deploy additional instances of services quickly and efficiently as demand dictates. This can happen automatically and is crucial during times of heavy system use. Furthermore, Docker facilitates load balancing and microservices architecture, which are essential for distributing the system's operations across multiple servers, thereby enhancing performance, and reducing bottlenecks.

The implementation of Docker within ENVISION's infrastructure reflects a forward-thinking approach to system design. It anticipates future growth and ensures that the system can evolve without being constrained by its initial configurations.

1.1.13 Integration and Communication

At the core of ENVISION's integration strategy are RESTful APIs — the standard architecture for implementing networked communications. RESTful APIs provide a straightforward approach to building web services that allow for easy exchange of data between different parts of the system. In ENVISION, RESTful APIs serve as the backbone for communication, enabling the frontend user interface to interact dynamically with the backend logic layer. These APIs ensure that requests from the users, such as data queries or service invocations, are translated into the appropriate backend operations, and the results are returned in a consumable format.

The communication between the frontend and backend is a critical aspect of ENVISION's functionality. When users interact with the user interface — whether they are querying crop classification, distinction of organic farming practices, or visualizing geospatial information — the frontend leverages RESTful APIs to send these requests to the backend. The backend, with its integrated databases and processing services, executes the necessary operations and then communicates the results back to the frontend. This back-and-forth is seamless, often occurring in real-time, and is imperceptible to the user, who experiences a fluid and responsive interface.

Data flow within ENVISION is meticulously orchestrated. From the moment data enters the system, be it through direct user input or integrated from third-party applications, it is managed and routed with precision. RESTful APIs facilitate the movement of this data through various services and processes.

1.2 Design of backend and frontend

1.2.1 Description of ENVISION components

Figure 2: Description of ENVISION components

- a. The **Business Layer** is the core of the system. It is responsible for receiving the parcel data from the paying agencies/ certification bodies and the products from the service providers. Furthermore, it is responsible for serving the final results to the end-users with the visualization of the data. The Business Layer is composed by the following components:
 - i. The **Web API (REST)** that is responsible for the communication between the User Interface Layer (Mobile and Web Applications) and the Business Layer. The Web API opens an interface that allows the users to import parcel data (i.e. geometry, declared crop type, declared area, etc.) and view the results of the services. Additionally, it allows the service providers to retrieve these parcel data, which are input to the products/ services. The WEB API is developed with the Django framework and all the connections use the HTTP/TLS protocol.
 - ii. The **Parcel Import Service**, which parses the Parcel Declaration File (a shp file with pre-defined fields/ columns/ information) provided by the end-users and saves the distinct parcels and their data in the storage layer. This service is triggered when end-users upload the Parcel Declaration Files.
 - iii. The **Product Import Service**, which is responsible for receiving the products and the EO-based derived results for each parcel and saving them to the data storage layer. This service is triggered when one of the following actions occurs:
 1. The service providers upload the results.
 2. A periodic process requests and fetches results (when available) from the services providers.

- iv. The **Notification Service** which is responsible for sending email notifications to the end-users when the services identify deviations from the declared information (from the declaration files).
 - v. The **OGC Service**, which is powered by the Geoserver, will be consumed by the mapping subsystems of the Web and Mobile applications to provide the end-users with data visualisation.
- b. The **Storage Layer** is responsible for storing the parcel data and their results. The Storage Layer is composed by the following components:
- i. The **Postgres/PostGIS database** that is responsible for the storage of the parcels' spatial data and the classification and numeric results. The Postgres/PostGIS database is integrated with the Geoserver via the Postgres/PostGIS driver. Furthermore, the database stores several file metadata that are used in the integration between the Geoserver and the Database. The data saved in the database come from both end-users and service providers.
 - ii. The **File System** that is used for storing file data, like rasters and shapefiles. These files usually come from the service providers.
 - iii. The **Redis ephemeral database**, which is used as a supporting queueing mechanism by the Parcel Import Service for minimising long internet connections during the parcel import process. More specifically, when end-users upload a Parcel Declaration File the process of parsing the file is added to the Redis queue, but it is not executed immediately in order to keep the connection between the User Interface Layer and the Business Layer short. After the connection closes, the Parcel Import Service picks up the process from the Redis queue and starts importing the parcel data into the storage layer.
- c. The **User Interface Layer** which is responsible for the communication between the end-users (including the farmers) and the system. All components of the User Interface Layer communicate with the Business Layer via the REST Web API using the HTTPS protocol via a secure Authentication and Authorization Service. The User Interface Layer is composed by the following components:
- i. The Web Application, through which the end-users (paying agencies and certification bodies) can view and interact with the system. Specifically, through the Web Application the end-users can import parcels, view the results based on their business case and filter them in various ways (i.e. view all the parcels with misclassified crop type, etc.). This part of the interface is build using Vue.js.
 - ii. The Mobile Application, through which the farmers can view parcel-based results. Specifically, through the Mobile Application the farmers can see data referring to their own parcels and submit additional information (i.e. upload of geotagged/ timestamped photos). This part of the interface is built using Vue.js and Capacitor.

1.2.2 Data flow

The user Authentication process:

The **Authentication Service** that is responsible for authenticating and authorising the connections to the Business Layer done by the end-users. The Authentication Service is powered by Keycloak which

uses the OpenID Connect protocol for all connections. This service allows the platform to restrict users from having access to specific content so that different business cases cannot obtain data of other business cases.

In more detail, the end-users connect to a component of the User Interface Layer and fill in their credentials. Then, the corresponding component connects to the Authentication Service and attempts to exchange the user credentials with a web token. If the credentials are correct, the Authentication Service provides the token. The User Interface component now can use the token in every connection with the Web API. Every time the Web API receives a connection request, it validates the connection's token with the Authentication Service. If the token is valid, the Web API proceeds with the User Interface request. Finally, to avoid the security risk of using the same token repeatedly, the web token expires after a few minutes. In that case, the Authentication Service obligates the User Interface component to request a new token using the refresh token mechanism.

The Parcel Import process

The Parcel Import process starts when the end-users (paying agencies and certification bodies) upload a Parcel Declaration File to the Web Application of the User Interface Layer. The Web Application sends the file to the Business Layer through the Web API. Then, the Web API saves the file temporarily in the File System and initiates the Parcel Import Service. The Parcel Import Service saves the job of parsing the file to the Redis Job Queue, without executing it. After the connection between the Web Application and Web API closes, the Parcel Import Service picks up the job from the Redis queue and starts parsing the Parcel Declaration File. More specifically, it stores the parcels' geospatial information with additional data (i.e. parcel id, farming practices, crop type, etc.), in the PostGIS database.

The Product import process

The product import (service integration) process refers to the receipt/import of the services' results regarding the parcels stored in the system. The business layer receives the parcel results in two ways; in the first way the product import is initiated by the service providers, whereas the second way the process is initialised by the system which fetches the results by the service providers.

In the first case, the service providers initialise the connection with the system by sending files with geospatial information to the business layer via the Web API. Then, the Web API passes the file to the Product Import Service, which is responsible for storing the file in the File System, and adds the file as a layer to the Geoserver.

In the second case, the Product Import Service initialises the connection among the service providers and the system. For instance, the Product Import Service collects periodically the results produced by NOA, by connecting to the NOA's database, via SSH tunnelling. Then, the Product Import Service runs queries in the NOA's database and saves the results in the ENVISION's PostGIS database. In a similar manner, the Product Import Service periodically fetches the results produced by Agroapps, by requesting data from the Agroapps API and saving them in the ENVISION's PostGIS database and File System.

The data serving process

The parcel data are served to the farmers via the Mobile Application, to the paying agencies/certification bodies via the Web Application and to the service providers via the Web API. All these three user categories have specific restrictions and they are allowed to have access to different data levels. The restrictions are realised by using the Authentication Service processes. In the back-end, both Web and Mobile Applications request data from the Web API, so in fact all users get data through

the Web API. However, there is a difference between the process of serving geospatial data and the rest. For instance, regarding the geospatial data, like the parcel visualization on top of the map, all User Interface Layer requests to the Web API are redirected to the OGC service. The OGC service fetches the data from the File System or the PostGIS database and transforms them based on the OGC specifications requested by the User Interface Layer. On the other hand, regarding the requests of non-geospatial data to the Web API, the Web API requests the data from the PostGIS database and returns a response in JSON format.

2 ENVISION Services Specifications

This chapter provides a description of each data product that will be developed including the internal and external dependencies as well as dependencies from each other.

Table 1: ENVISION data products

ID	Related Task	Data Product	Business Case	Services	Service Provider
DP1	Task 3.3	Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series	NMA	Harvest events detection	NOA
			NMA & CAPO	Stubble burning identification on arable land	
			CAPO	Detection of illegal land clearing in Natura2000 protection areas	
			NMA & CAPO	Minimum soil cover for soil erosion	
			NMA & CAPO	Runoff risk assessment for the reduction of water pollution in nitrate vulnerable areas	
DP2	Task 3.4	Cultivated crop type maps	NMA & CAPO	Confirmation of GSAA	NOA
				Smart sampling for OTSC inspections	
				Crops diversification compliance	
DP3	Task 3.5	Grassland mowing events detection	NMA	Grassland activity monitoring and management	NOA
DP4	Task 3.6	Soil condition monitoring	LV	Top-soil qualitative soil organic carbon estimations	EV ILVO
DP5	Task 3.7	Crop growth Monitoring and identification of organic	OCS	Distinction of organic farming practices	AgroApps
				Crop growth monitoring	

		farming practices			
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2.1 Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series (AVSIT)

2.1.1 Services offered/Service Provider

This data product is designed to analyze time-series data related to vegetation and soil indices in Lithuania and Cyprus. It offers several algorithmic components:

- Minimum Soil Cover for Soil Erosion: This feature provides data on soil percentage and minimum soil cover, which helps assess the risk of soil erosion in different regions of Lithuania and Cyprus, particularly in agricultural areas. It can assist in making informed land management decisions to prevent soil erosion.
- Runoff Risk Assessment for the Reduction of Water Pollution in Nitrate Vulnerable Areas: This component assesses the risk of runoff and water pollution in nitrate vulnerable areas of Lithuania and Cyprus. It can be valuable in managing and mitigating water pollution, especially in regions with intense agricultural activities.
- Stubble Burning Identification: This component is designed to detect and identify instances of stubble burning, which can be a concern for air quality and environmental impact. It can help monitor and enforce regulations related to stubble burning practices.
- Harvest Event Detection: This feature identifies the occurrence of harvest events in agricultural arable areas of Lithuania. It can be used to track crop harvesting seasons, optimize farm operations, and monitor crop yields.
- Detection of illegal land clearing in Natura2000 protection areas: This feature is designed to identify unauthorized agricultural activities within Natura 2000 regions of Cyprus, ensuring the preservation of their ecological integrity and facilitating the monitoring of potential violations.

The Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series (AVSIT) applied for the Lithuanian and Cypriot pilot cases. The product made multiple classification of the crops throughout the year to ensure the confidence of the classification process. To ensure high accuracy, the system utilizes Sentinel-2 data. The provider of the service is NOA, whereas the results of the service are provided either via a RESTful API or as shape files.

2.1.2 Brief description of the data product

The Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series (AVSIT) represents an Earth Observation (EO) monitoring module designed to harness satellite data on top of the datacube. Its primary objective is to provide users with realistic insights pertaining to agricultural field activities and the enforcement of cross-compliance policies. This innovative module capitalizes on the extensive capabilities of the Datacube, introducing a cutting-edge Big Data framework for the purpose of monitoring the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) by Paying Agencies (PAs).

The central focus of AVSIT lies in the analysis of vegetation and soil index time-series data, with the intention of automatically detecting trends and identifying areas and conditions of elevated risk. This

analytical approach is aimed at significantly reducing the time that researchers and decision-makers traditionally allocate to the manual examination and identification of such cases.

To fulfill this mission, AVSIT has developed extensive, long-term time series datasets encompassing a variety of vegetation indices. These datasets are tailor-made to cater to the specific requirements of national-scale agricultural land monitoring in Lithuania and Cyprus. In addition to vegetation analysis, the module undertakes soil monitoring and employs sophisticated techniques for the identification of stubble burning events. This multifaceted approach is integral to the maintenance and monitoring of organic matter in soil, while also ensuring compliance with CAP regulations, statutory management requirements (SMRs), and the stipulations governing good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs).

Minimum soil cover for soil erosion

Monitoring of soil management is necessary to maintain a minimum soil cover over agricultural parcels of Lithuania and Cyprus. This is particularly emphasized in the context of GAEC 4, which is designed to safeguard soil against erosion during the vulnerable period following the harvest season and extending through the winter months. It underscores the importance of preserving soil integrity by ensuring that parcels are not left bare or exposed after the harvest of crops. The rule is primarily aimed at preventing soil erosion, which can occur due to factors such as heavy rainfall, wind, or other environmental forces when the soil lacks adequate cover. By maintaining a minimum soil cover, agricultural practices can help to retain soil structure, fertility, and overall health, which is crucial for sustainable farming and environmental conservation.

Runoff Risk Assessment for the Reduction of Water Pollution in Nitrate Vulnerable Areas

In order to answer the statutory management requirement and SMR 1, a runoff risk assessment for the reduction of water pollution in nitrate vulnerable areas was developed in both Lithuania and Cyprus, taking into account the proximity to the closest surface waters. The aim of the rule is to protect water against the runoff of nitrate polluted soil and water that could possibly reach fresh surface waters nearby. The requirements restrict storage, application of fertiliser and pesticides and cultivations along watercourses. In this direction, the usage of nitrogen fertilizer is accepted in parcels located more than 10m away from streams, 50m away from rivers and lakes and finally 300m away from any source used for water supply. Therefore, distance from every point of the parcel's geometry to the closest water surface is calculated. Parcels that are above a certain distance threshold are excluded. Afterwards, according to bibliography, several models have been developed to identify the probability or size of soil erosion. The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) are the most widely used and accepted empirical soil erosion models.

Stubble Burning Identification

The detection and mapping of burnt areas are crucial for environmental agencies and agricultural monitoring. Stubble Burning Identification is a key requirement for compliance monitoring, particularly

for the Lithuanian and Cypriot paying agency. This task focuses on utilizing satellite imagery, specifically Sentinel-2 data, to detect stubble burning events in arable areas.

Harvest event detection

The agricultural monitoring practices prioritize the detection of harvest events, particularly for arable land parcels designated for Ecological Focus Area (EFA) practices as per the GSAA. The objective of this task is to identify the parcels that have undergone harvesting within the cultivation period and determine the compliance level based on the regulations of the Lithuanian paying agency. To achieve this, a harvest detection algorithm is employed, leveraging a combination of VIs derived from Sentinel-2 SITS. The algorithm generates a map that highlights the parcels where harvest events have been detected, along with the corresponding dates of these events.

Natura 2000 Hotspot Detection

Natura 2000 is a network of protected areas in the European Union aiming to assure the long-term survival of Europe's most valuable and threatened species and habitats. As expected, any agricultural intervention in land inside Natura 2000 sites is prohibited, except special permission has been given. Additionally, Natura policies are not applicable to parcels declared as arable land inside these protected sites, before Natura 2000 was put into effect. For this purpose, an intensive activity detection routine have been developed to locate areas of intense activity within Natura 2000 regions of Cyprus using vegetation signatures evaluation. This routine utilizes satellite imagery and evaluates vegetation and soil indices to identify pixels that show significant changes associated with intense activity. The routine requires users to provide the specific Natura 2000 regions of interest for analysis.

2.1.3 External dependencies

Databases, Hubs, Libraries

- Python
- OSGEO/ GDAL Library
- NumPy and Pandas Libraries
- Datacube API for connecting to the cube

2.1.4 Literature on the service/ product

The CAP requirements responsible for reducing the water pollution in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs) (SMR 1 rule), among other things, requests the farmers to perform themselves risk assessment on the susceptibility of a parcel to contribute nitrate-rich soil to nearby surface water. The assessment shall involve the following considerations:

- The slope of the land, especially if over 12°
- Ground cover
- Proximity to surface water
- Weather conditions
- Soil type and condition
- The presence of land drains.

Based on the requirements of the risk assessment, it can be easily seen that emphasis has been given on the soil erosion and runoff susceptibility. Since the monitoring and estimation of the above conditions, only via means of Sentinel-2 remote sensing was not possible; an alternative approach has been devised. The Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) and the revised version RUSLE are very common soil erosion modeling techniques¹². The soil loss equation is considered to be an appropriate proxy for the estimation of risk in terms of the SMR 1 requirements.

The combined use of GIS and erosion models, such as USLE/RUSLE, has been proved to be an effective approach for estimating the magnitude and spatial distribution of erosion and soil loss^{3,4,5}. Five major factors such as rainfall pattern, soil type, topography, crop system, and management practices were used in USLE/RUSLE for computing the expected average soil loss through the following equation⁶

Figure 3: Overall RUSLE values in parcel scale

$$A = R \times K \times L \times S \times C \times P$$

where A is the computed spatial average soil loss and temporal average soil loss per unit area per year (t/ha year-1), R is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor [MJ mm/(ha h year-1)], K is the soil erodibility factor [t ha h/(ha MJ mm)], L is the slope length factor, S is the slope steepness factor, C is the cover management factor, and P is the conservation support practice factor. L, S, C, and P are all dimensionless. Individual GIS layers have been generated for each factor in the RUSLE equation and combined at parcel-scale to spatially predict the soil loss.

The proximity to surface water accounts for the parcel's slope orientation and its relation to the proximity orientation. Therefore, multiple parcels can be completely exempted from the proximity risk assessment as their slope orientation is significantly deviating from the proximity orientation. As a results specific threshold of acceptable orientation angle differences has been set in order to indicate perilous cases.

¹ Panagos, P., Borrelli, P. & Meusburger, K. (2015). A New European Slope Length and Steepness Factor (LS-Factor) for Modeling Soil Erosion by Water. *Geosciences*, 5(2), 117-126.

² Panagos, P., Borrelli, P. & Meusburger, K., Alewell, C., Lugato, E. & Montanarella, L. (2015). Estimating the Soil Erosion Cover-management Factor at the European Scale. *Land Use Policy*, 48, 38-50.

³ Yitayew, M., Pokrzywka, S. J. & Renard, K.G. (1999). Using GIS for facilitating erosion estimation. *Applied Engineering in Agriculture*, 15(4), doi: 10.13031/2013.5780.

⁴ Fernandez, C., Wu, J.Q., McCool, D. & Stockle, C. (2003). Estimating water erosion and sediment yield with GIS, RUSLE, and SEDD. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 58(3), 128-136.

⁵ Wu, Q. & Wang, M. (2007). A framework for risk assessment on soil erosion by water using an integrated and systematic approach. *Journal of Hydrology*, 337(1-2), 11-21.

⁶ Renard, K.G., Foster, G.R., Weesies, G.A. & Porter, J.P. (1991). RUSLE, Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*. 46(1), 30-33.

Figure 4: Special Case of an exempted parcel according to water proximity method

The SMR 1: NVZ Water Pollution clearly identifies the requirement for the risk assessment of runoff of polluted water and soil into surface water. Since the risk assessment requirement heavily depend on soil erosivity and erodibility, the RUSLE method of soil loss estimation was considered appropriate. The RUSLE product functions as a proxy to the susceptibility of each parcel to lose soil outside its boundaries.

On the other end, the proximity to surface water function is the second quantitative output of the methodology; where together with RUSLE form a look-up table of combinations between the two values, estimating the overall risk. The proximity-to-surface-water attribute accounts for the orientation overlap between the proximity orientation and the overall parcel slope orientation. This way, only parcels that could actually contribute polluted soil and water to nearby watercourses will be recorded.

Unfortunately, for the validation of the proposed method, actual SMR 1 compliance records should be available. At this point the algorithm attempts to understand in depth the requirements of the risk assessment of SMR and propose solid and verified GIS and RS techniques to tackle the respective elements of the rule. Finally, the product in question could also be exploited for the identification of parcels that ought to comply with the buffer zones defined in the GAEC 1: Buffer Strips CC requirement.

2.1.5 Input data

1. Satellite:
 - a. Lithuania
 - i. Sentinel-2 L2A (tiles: 34UEG, 34UFE, 34UFF, 34UFG, 34UGE, 34VEH, 34VFH, 35ULA, 35ULB, 35ULV, 35UMA, 35UMB, 35VLC, 35VMC)
 1. Spectral bands (B01-B12)
 2. Scene Classification (SCL)
 - b. Cyprus
 - i. Sentinel-2 L2A (tiles: 36SWD, 36SVD)
 1. Spectral bands (B01-B12)
 2. Scene Classification (SCL)
2. Products and Geospatial data:
 - a. LPIS

- b. farmers' declarations (GSAA)
 - c. Annual soil loss layer
 - d. Rainfall erosivity factor layer
 - e. Soil erodibility factor layer
 - f. Slope length factor and slope steepness factor layer
 - g. Crop and cover management factor layer
 - h. Conservation supporting practices factor layer
 - i. Slope - DEM
3. Paying agencies:
- a. Geospatial data (LPIS, GSAA): Parcels geometries and farmers declarations as a shapefile (updated when is necessary)
 - b. A lookup table for all the available crop type names, codes, families and CD ancillary info
 - c. Events Timestamps to fine-tune the algorithms (Stubble Burning, Harvest of arable land)
 - d. Agricultural Practices Descriptions – National CAP strategic Plans
 - e. Hydrographic Network
 - f. Natura2000 regions

2.1.6 Output data

The product offers five distinct output components based on the specific delivery requirements of end users:

1. A shapefile indicating bare soil percentage and minimum soil cover alerts for soil erosion.
2. A shapefile of Runoff Risk level map of parcels within nitrate vulnerable zones.
3. A Shapefile identifying stubble burning events on arable land, including dates of the events detected at the parcel level.
4. A shapefile for tracking harvest events on arable cultivations, including dates of the events detected at the parcel level.
5. A shapefile for Natura2000 Hotspot Detection in geometrical points based showing the alert pixels detected.

Table 2: Output data for the Analytics on Vegetation and Soil Index Time-series

Short description	File type	Expected size	Frequency
Minimum Soil Cover for Soil Erosion	Shapefile	20MB (Lithuania) 20MB (Cyprus)	1/year (Lithuania) 1/year (Cyprus)
Runoff Risk Assessment for the Reduction of Water Pollution in Nitrate Vulnerable Areas	Shapefile	200MB (Lithuania) 200MB (Cyprus)	1/year (Lithuania) 1/year (Cyprus)
Stubble Burning Identification	Shapefile	1MB (Lithuania) 1MB (Cyprus)	1/year (Lithuania) 1/year (Cyprus)

Harvest Event Detection	Shapefile	400MB (Lithuania)	3/year (Lithuania)
Detection of illegal land clearing in Natura2000 protection areas	Shapefile	2MB (Cyprus)	1/year (Cyprus)

2.2 Cultivated Crop Type Maps (CCTM)

2.2.1 Services offered/Service Provider

The CCTM product includes the following features:

- Confirmation of applicants' declarations (based on GSAA): Utilizes machine learning techniques to classify crop types dynamically throughout the entire cultivation period or confirm the declared crop types. Additionally, the provision of a homogeneity marker (only for the case of Cyprus) can assist on the detection of multi-cultures and the presence of multiple cultivations within a single field.
- A traffic light alert system to identify potential false declarations, using smart sampling algorithms
- Assessment of crop compliance with the Greening-1 rule for Crop Diversification, ensuring adherence to regulations.

The Cultivated Crop Type Maps (CCTM) has been applied for the Lithuanian and Cypriot pilot cases. The product made multiple classification of the crops throughout the year to ensure the confidence of the classification process. To ensure high accuracy, the system utilizes both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. The provider of the service is NOA, whereas the results of the service are provided either via a RESTful API or as shape files.

2.2.2 Brief description of the data product

The Cultivated Crop Type Maps (CCTM) is an Earth Observation (EO) crop classification module that exploits satellite data along with the usage of Machine Learning techniques in order to provide products related to the validation of the declared crop type by a farmer. In addition, it provides the knowledge of the compliance with certain environmental rules such as Greening requirements. Thus, it can be used from the Paying Agencies as a tool to enhance the process of checking the declarations of the farmers at the time of declarations, but also to assist via smart sampling of parcel to be checked during the validation process (OTSCs). This can be achieved as the service that informs the PAs about the parcels that have a high probability of being wrongly declared. The Crop Diversification Service exploits the Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) and the declarations of the farmers (GSAA). For the case of Cyprus a homogeneity marker is derived, in order to address the challenge of multiple crop types within a single parcel declaration, facilitating confirmation of farmers' declarations, eligibility verification and precise crop mapping by quantifying spectral variation. As a result, the predicted crop type of each declared parcel is generated along with a percentage of prediction's confidence and it is used as an indicator for the declaration process.

Confirmation of Declaration:

A declaration's conformity assessment is determined based on the alignment between the crop type declared by the farmer and the classification results. This classification system helps determine whether the parcel's crop type declaration matches the model's predictions with the necessary level of confidence, making it clear when the classification is reliable, unreliable, or falls in between.

One of the common challenges faced in Cyprus is the issue of multiple crop types being cultivated within the same parcel. Resolving this issue is crucial for confirmation of farmers' declaration (GSAA) and ensuring eligibility verification, and compliance with agricultural policies. Moreover, this practice can create difficulties in accurate crop mapping and monitoring of agricultural activities, as it becomes challenging to determine the specific crop types and their respective areas within the parcel. To address this, an algorithm has been developed to create a supplementary homogeneity indicator that can highlight such cases. The presence of multiple crops within a single field often leads to significant spectral variation within the parcel. As a result, the algorithm aims to quantify this intra-parcel variation and provide an indicator of homogeneity.

Smart Sampling for OTSC (traffic light alert system)

Smart sampling is a sophisticated algorithm that is evolving dynamically throughout the cultivation period by taking advantage of both the current and the previously generated Crop Type Maps {t, t-1, t-2, t-3, ...}, in order to identify the most confident misclassifications. In essence, by taking into account the confidence level, which is based on the logit probabilities, as well as the logits' difference between the two most probable categories indicated by the ML classifier, we can identify misclassifications that we expect to be false declarations rather than false predictions.

The basis of the methodology is what we call a "traffic light" alert system. This system enables the categorization of parcels into four classes, based on the classification model's confidence scores.

Crop Diversification (CD) Compliance Map

The Crop Diversification exploits the Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) and the Geospatial Aid applications (GSAA). Crop diversification is a key component of the greening measures, which requires farmers to cultivate at least two different crops on their arable land, with the main crop covering no more than 75% of the area. Crop diversification is an essential element in the greening of the CAP, promoting sustainability, biodiversity, and the long-term health of European agricultural landscapes. It encourages farmers to adopt more environmentally friendly and resilient agricultural practices while supporting the broader goals of the CAP. CD compliance map is a compilation of "if conditions" according to the greening 1 set of rules.

2.2.3 External dependencies

Databases, Hubs, Libraries

1. Python
2. OSGEO/ GDAL Library
3. Scikit-learn, NumPy and Pandas Libraries

4. Datacube API for connecting to the cube

2.2.4 Literature on the service/ product

The CAP includes a series of rules and practices to monitor the land cover and control the subsidy payments. Paying Agencies are responsible for the distribution of CAP funds based on the farmers' declarations and their compliance to the CAP⁷. The crop classification enhances the procedure of validation in terms of accuracy and time. Remote sensing data contribute to the crop type classification process⁸ along with the Machine Learning techniques such as support vector machines^{9,10} and random forest¹¹. The usage of both optical and SAR data enhances the feature space required for the crop classification service. Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B constellation results 5-day revisiting frequency and is widely used in crop classification^{12,13}. Nonetheless, the existence of clouds, especially in certain areas, become a drawback as the optical radiation cannot penetrate them. This drawback is strongly related to the classification performance¹⁴. To solve this problem, integrated SAR and InSAR observations have been widely used in order to deal with the problem of frequent clouds and improve accuracy. To that direction, research¹⁵ has proposed a more careful feature selection and proper combination of them that will drive to the better interpretability of the respective predictive models and more efficient management of computation expenses. In addition, taking into consideration the significant impact of parcels' size, shape and boundaries will assist on the design of more robust ML training routines. Finally, based on the respective work of Sentinel-Hub¹⁶, we derived an homogeneity marker (also provided by DIONE project (<https://zenodo.org/records/7116922>)) to overcome the challenge of multiple crop types within a single parcel declaration, an algorithm has been developed to quantify spectral variation, enhancing eligibility verification and precise crop mapping.

2.2.5 Input data

More specifically we utilize the following data:

1. Satellite:
 - a. Lithuania
 - i. Sentinel-2 L2A (tiles: 34UEG, 34UFE, 34UFF, 34UFG, 34UGE, 34VEH, 34VFH, 35ULA, 35ULB, 35ULV, 35UMA, 35UMB, 35VLC, 35VMC)
 1. Spectral bands (B01-B12)
 2. Scene Classification (SCL)
 - ii. Sentinel-1 GRD (rel. orbits: 29, 58, 131, 160)

⁷ Sitokonstantinou, V., Papoutsis, I., Kontoes, C., Lafarga Arnal, A., Armesto, A.A. & Garraza, Z.J. (2018). Scalable Parcel-Based Crop Identification Scheme Using Sentinel-2 Data Time-Series for the Monitoring of the Common Agricultural Policy. *Remote Sensing*, 10(6), 911. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10060911>

⁸ Rousi, M., Sitokonstantinou, V., Meditskos, G., Papoutsis, I., Gialampoukidis, I., Koukos, A., Karathanassi, V., Drivas, T., Vrochidis, S., Kontoes, C. & Kompatsiaris, I. (2020). Semantically Enriched Crop Type Classification and Linked Earth Observation Data to Support the Common Agricultural Policy Monitoring. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 14, 529-552, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2020.3038152.

⁹ Duro, D.C., Franklin, S.E. & Dubé, M.G. (2012). A comparison of pixel-based and object-based image analysis with selected machine learning algorithms for the classification of agricultural landscapes using SPOT-5 HRG imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 118, 259-272, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2011.11.020>

¹⁰ Ok, A., Akar, O., Gungor, O. (2012). Evaluation of random forest method for agricultural crop classification. *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 45(3), 421-432.

¹¹ Raczek, E. & Zagajewski, B. (2017). Comparison of support vector machine, random forest and neural network classifiers for tree species classification on airborne hyperspectral APEX images. *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 50(1), 144-154.

¹² Immitzer, M., Vuolo, F., Atzberger, C. (2016) First experience with Sentinel-2 data for crop and tree species classifications in central Europe. *Remote Sensing*, 8(3), 166, doi: 10.3390/rs8030166.

¹³ Sonobe, R., Yamaya, Y., Tani, H., Wang, X., Kobayashi, N. & Mochizuki, K. (2018). Crop classification from Sentinel-2-derived vegetation indices using ensemble learning. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 12(02), doi: 10.1117/1.JRS.12.026019.

¹⁴ Whitcraft, A.K., Vermote, E.F., Becker-Reshef, I. & Justice, C.O. (2015). Cloud cover throughout the agricultural growing season: Impacts on passive optical earth observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 156, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.10.009

¹⁵ Orynbaikyzy, A., Gessner, U., Mack, B. & Conrad, C. (2020). Crop Type Classification Using Fusion of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 Data: Assessing the Impact of Feature Selection, Optical Data Availability, and Parcel Sizes on the Accuracies. *Remote Sensing*, 12(2779), doi: 10.3390/rs12172779.

¹⁶ Jernej Puc, Sentinelhub - Area Monitoring — Homogeneity Marker, Oct 13 2020: <https://medium.com/sentinel-hub/area-monitoring-homogeneity-marker-742047b834dc>

1. Backscattering coefficients (VV-VH)
 - b. Cyprus
 - i. Sentinel-2 L2A (tiles: 36SWD, 36SVD)
 1. Spectral bands (B01-B12)
 2. Scene Classification (SCL)
 - ii. Sentinel-1 GRD (rel. orbits: 94,167)
 1. Backscattering coefficients (VV-VH)
2. Paying agencies:
 - a. Geospatial data (LPIS, GSAA): Parcels geometries and farmers declarations as a shapefile (updated when is necessary)
 - b. A lookup table for all the available crop type names, codes, families and CD ancillary info (Table 3)
 - c. Agricultural Practices Descriptions – National CAP strategic Plans

Table 3: Look-up Table sample schema

ID	CROP CODE	CROP NAME	CROP FAMILY	EAA	AL	PGrass	TGrass	Fallow	Cwater	Protein	Cother
1	C1	FALLOW	FALLOW	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
2	C2	SPRING BARLEY	ANNUAL CROPS	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	C3	WINTER WHEAT	WINTER CEREAL	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	C4	PASTURE	GRASSLAND	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
5	C5	WALNUT	PERMANENT CROPS	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	C6	WINTER RAPE	WINTER RAPE	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

2.2.6 Output data

The product is providing an output shapefile consist of:

- Dynamic crop type maps over the registered parcels for every new or group of new Sentinel acquisitions.
- A homogeneity marker (for the case of Cyprus) for the detection of multi-cultures and the presence of multiple cultivations within a single field.
- Traffic light maps over the registered parcels for smart sampling of on-the-spot inspections and early alert of the users.
- Crops Diversification (Greening-1) compliance map over the registered parcels at the end of the cultivation period.

Table 4: Output data for the Cultivated Crop Type Maps

Short description	File type	Expected size	Frequency
Cultivated Crop Type Maps	Shapefile	1GB (Lithuania) 200MB (Cyprus)	6/year (Lithuania) 4/year (Cyprus)

2.3 Grassland Mowing Events Detection

2.3.1 Services offered/Service Provider

Grassland Mowing Detection is another ENVISION data product which consists of 2 individual pre-processing steps:

- Data Fusion
- Mowing Events Detection Algorithms and Management of Activity (compliance check)

The Grassland Mowing Events Detection has been implemented in the Lithuanian pilot cases. This product involves multiple iterations throughout the year for optimal accuracy. To mitigate the challenge of extensive cloud coverage, the system leverages both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. The provider of the service is NOA, whereas the results of the service are provided either via a RESTful API or as shape files.

2.3.2 Brief description of the data product

Data Fusion

The Data Fusion (DFS) workflow combines Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data in order to "increase" the availability of cloud-free observations. Optical sensors, like Sentinel-2, are sensitive to clouds resulting in gaps in time series data. On the other hand, Sentinel-1 data are not affected by clouds and can provide valuable information in the presence of cloud obstructions. Hence, we exploit Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 complementary nature to generate cloud-free Sentinel-2 time series through a sophisticated Deep Neural Network architecture. The cloud-free time series are then integrated into the ENVISION DataCube and utilized as input for various services, including the Grassland Mowing Events Detection. The service provides complete S2 time series for the NDVI of every pixel, acting as an ancillary interpolation routine in order to replace the respective cloudy observations.

Mowing Events Detection Algorithm

Then, the Grassland Mowing Events Detection module exploits the newly constructed data obtained from the Data Fusion service, utilizing either Deep Learning algorithms (if label data are available) or a threshold-based alternative approach. When labeled data is provided, a Deep Learning algorithm is employed to analyze the satellite data and identify specific patterns and features associated with grassland mowing events. The algorithm is learning from the labeled examples to make predictions and detect the time ranges where mowing events have occurred. In the absence of labeled data, a threshold-based approach is available, similar to the methodology employed for harvest events detection. By defining specific thresholds or criteria based on relevant parameters, such as steep changes in artificially created NDVI. Both approaches aim to accurately detect and track grassland mowing events.

This information provides valuable insights into the temporal dynamics of grassland activity, enabling effective monitoring and management of agricultural practices. This information can be used from the PAs to estimate the compliancy of the farmers with regards to the national mowing regulations or for

the quantification of the grasslands activity for sustainable management. Similarly, the mowing event maps are populating the CAP monitoring ENVISION DataCube as soon as they are produced. Thus, we can also create specific geo-queries and extract summary statistics for particular spatial and temporal conditions. One example of such a query would be to retrieve the mowing intensity profile of a predefined area.

2.3.3 External dependencies

Databases, Hubs, Libraries

1. Python
2. OSGEO/ GDAL Library
3. Tensorflow and Pytorch
4. Scikit-learn, NumPy and Pandas Libraries
5. Datacube API for connecting to the cube

2.3.4 Literature on the service/ product

In order to address the challenge of mowing detection, data of HR and VHR optical and SAR imagery are provided for the computation of vegetation parameters indicative for the current grassland condition, managing to detect the various anomalies and changes on index profiles.

Researchers using BFAST toolbox¹⁷ are able to detect potential changes as well as the magnitude of these on vicinal regions in north-western Slovenia. Exploiting data of Sentinel-2 and constructing the respective NDVI, they applied a pixel-based BFAST monitor time-series analysis and a semi-automated methodology. The above has been examined for meadows and crop fields respectively. BFAST performs a decomposition into the signal trends, seasonal and remained components in order to pinpoint anomalies in the total behaviour of the investigated index. However, since it is susceptible to overestimation on the number of anomalies of permanent meadows candidates due to the short time series and trend overestimation, it is followed and supplemented by a parcel-based graph analysis (descriptive statistics) and a pixel-based time-series standard deviation computing in order to verify these results.

Researchers¹⁸ constructed a grassland mowing index (GMI) based on the NDVI and its sudden drops from consecutive clear observations in their disposal extracted from areas of Switzerland as it displays a more representative image of the mowing events and characterizes mowing schedule and frequency according to the Swiss regulations. Moreover, they performed different training scenarios for parcel and shrunken-parcel cases, as well as optimized situations (after various level of cloud masking - blue-band masking approach) in matter of time consumption against common ready-to-use algorithms. It is worthy to be mentioned the pixels allocation step into few grass/non-grass identified clusters (characterization was aided by careful visual inspection) in order to masked out from the NDVI time series before into-parcel aggregation level. All things considered significant findings showed that grassland mapping is not limited on the number of cloudless images as long as they are carefully selected and acquired in crucial moments of mowing season.

¹⁷ Kanjir, U., Duric, N. & Veljanovski, T. (2018). Sentinel-2 based temporal detection of agricultural land use anomalies in support of common agricultural policy monitoring. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(10), 405.

¹⁸ Kolečka, N., Ginzler, C., Pazur, R., Price, B. & Verburg, P. (2018). Regional scale mapping of grassland mowing frequency with sentinel-2 time series. *Remote Sensing*, 10(08), 1221.

On the contrary, in a not sophisticated methodology, a time-series algorithm¹⁹ has been presented based on the estimated NDVI from Sentinel-2 images for different regimes across Germany on 10-day composites on an effort to characterize mowing behavior and evaluate the acquired results based on in-situ data taken from farmers. Essentially, a 3rd order polynomial is fitted based on time-series vertices for every pixel available. Lastly, a mowing event is characterized when the respective residual between the NDVI points and the fitted polynomial overcomes a specific threshold.

Alternatively, Sentinel-1 data can be used for the estimation of mowing events. Research work has been conducted for the area of Rannu in Estonia where researchers have correlated polarization coherence of VV and VH transmission/receival for different relative orbit numbers (RON) and image resolutions (window-size) since the median values of those measures can present remarkable soaring trends even after 24 to 36 days of an actual mowing event compared to pre-event values.

All in all, other researchers^{20,21} are using Sentinel-1 SAR acquisitions in order to tackle the problem of scarce optical imagery and low temporal resolution since it is highly affected from the cloud coverage. For this reason, they formulate an estimated data-driven NDVI based on a RNN architecture and Sentinel-1 originated input data accompanied with an extra ancillary temporal information (day of year, month, season, etc.). However, issues have been arisen here since SAR signals characterized by high sensitivity and as a result S1 images are also affected by shadow, layover, and foreshortening (occurring differently between ascending and descending orbits). Auxiliary information provided aims to mitigate such predicament, acting as an attention vector using multiple supplementary data based on the region and time. Ultimately, the reconstructed NDVI obtained could be used as a starting point for the subsequent grassland analysis.

Monitoring of agricultural crops and grasslands is necessary for decision-making. In order to address the problem of frequent cloud cover that multiple regions present, especially in Northern geographical latitudes, systematic routines need to be developed exploiting SAR and InSAR data that are not affected from these obstacles, but also the already available cloud-free observations. To that direction multiple Deep Learning (DL) techniques have been tried out during the recent past years.

From a computer-vision perceptive based on the benchmark study of²² and cGANs (conditional Generative Adversarial Neural Networks) and pix2pix architecture, multiple attempts and highlighted works in low-level fusion task have been published. In the field of Earth Observation (EO), authors^{23,24,25} are proposing several Deep Learning approaches of SAR-to-Optical image translations using cGANS and CNN networks using SAR, InSAR and past cloud-free Optical images available as inputs.

However, SAR and InSAR data are vulnerable not only to climatic conditions such as atmospheric humidity and precipitation, but also to topographical factors of the AOI like slope and exposition.

¹⁹ Griffiths, P., Nendel, C., Pickert, J. & Hostert, P. (2019). Towards national-scale characterization of grassland use intensity from integrated sentinel-2 and Landsat time series. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 238, 111124.

²⁰ Garioud, A., Valero, S., Giordano, S. & Mallet, C. (2020). On the joint exploitation of optical and SAR satellite imagery for grassland monitoring. *ISPRS – International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, XLIII-B3-2020*, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B3-2020-591-202.

²¹ Garioud, A., Giordano, S., Valero, S. & Mallet, C. (2019). Challenges in grasslands mowing event detection with multimodal Sentinel images. 10th International Workshop on the Analysis of Multitemporal Remote Sensing Images (MultiTemp), Shanghai, China, doi: 10.1109/Multi-Temp.2019.8866914.

²² Isola, P., Zhu, J., Zhou, T. & Efros, A. (2017). Image-to-Image Translation with Conditional Adversarial Networks. *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 10.1109/CVPR.2017.632.

²³ Haas, J. & Ban, Y. (2017). Sentinel-1A SAR and Sentinel-2A MSI data fusion for urban ecosystem service mapping. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 8, doi: 10.1016/j.rsase.2017.07.006.

²⁴ Fuentes Reyes, M., Auer, S., Merkle, N., Henry, C. & Schmitt, M. (2019). SAR-to-Optical Image Translation Based on Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks—Optimization, Opportunities and Limits. *Remote Sensing*, 11, doi: 10.3390/rs11172067.

²⁵ Zhang, Q., Liu, X., Liu, M., Zou, X., Zhu, L. & Ruan, X. (2021). Comparative Analysis of Edge Information and Polarization on SAR-to-Optical Translation Based on Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 128. doi: 10.3390/rs13010128.

Taking into consideration the aforementioned, in their illuminated work^{26,27} are suggesting Recurrent Neural Networks and GRUs in order to take advantage of the temporal phenology characteristic that specific grasslands type presents, in an effort to ameliorate the performance of grassland monitoring and mowing events detection task.

Finally, others not that sophisticated models and methodologies have been advised using more common ML methodologies (e.g. Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, Boosting Algorithms, etc.) exploiting SAR time-series within the scope of Data Fusion for crop monitoring and crop type mapping^{28,29}.

2.3.5 Input data

More specifically we utilize the following data:

1. Satellite:
 - a. Lithuania
 - i. Sentinel-2 L2A (tiles: 34UEG, 34UFE, 34UFF, 34UFG, 34UGE, 34VEH, 34VFH, 35ULA, 35ULB, 35ULV, 35UMA, 35UMB, 35VLC, 35VMC)
 1. Spectral bands (B01-B12)
 2. Scene Classification (SCL)
 - ii. Sentinel-1 GRD (rel. orbits: 29, 58, 131, 160)
 1. Backscattering coefficients (VV-VH)
2. Paying agencies:
 - a. Geospatial data (LPIS, GSAA): Parcels geometries and farmers declarations as a shapefile (updated when is necessary)
 - b. Exact regulations characterize the grassland mowing or grazing policies. These files contain, among others, the maximum number of allowed mowing events and the exact period, during these events can take place.
 - c. Grassland's polygons to be check after CCTM as a shapefile
 - d. Agricultural Practices Descriptions – National CAP strategic Plans

2.3.6 Output data

The product is providing an output shapefile of:

- Dynamic Events Map of grassland mowing detection per parcel encapsulating all the extracted information regarding the detected events and their confidence levels.

Table 5: Output data for the Grassland Mowing Events Detection

Short description	File type	Expected size	Frequency
Grassland Mowing Events Detection	Shapefile	500MB (Lithuania)	6/year (Lithuania)

²⁶ Garioud, A., Giordano, S., Valero, S. & Mallet, C. (2019, August, 5-7). *Challenges in grasslands mowing event detection with multimodal Sentinel images*. 10th International Workshop on the Analysis of Multitemporal Remote Sensing Images (MultiTemp), Shanghai, China, doi: 10.1109/Multi-Temp.2019.8866914.

²⁷ Garioud, A., Valero, S., Giordano, S. & Mallet, C. (2020). On the joint exploitation of optical and SAR satellite imagery for grassland monitoring. *ISPRS – International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, XLIII-B3-2020*, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B3-2020-591-202.

²⁸ Filgueiras, R., Mantovani, E., Althoff, D., Fernandes-Filho, E. & Cunha, Fernando. (2019). Crop NDVI Monitoring Based on Sentinel 1. *Remote Sensing*, 11, doi: 10.3390/rs11121441.

²⁹ Filgueiras, R., Mantovani, E., Fernandes-Filho, E., Cunha, F., Althoff, D. & Dias, S.H. (2020). Fusion of MODIS and Landsat-Like Images for Daily High Spatial Resolution NDVI. *Remote Sensing*, 12, doi: 10.3390/rs12081297

2.4 Identification of organic farming practices

2.4.1 Services offered – Service provider

This service identifies whether a particular crop type declared as organic is classified as such, based on a traffic light system. The objectives of the product is to implement the training of classification algorithms with EO data, to predict farming practice at plot level for a specified crop type, and to report to the user information on the validity of the declaration in the form of a traffic light system that examines the following possibilities:

- a parcel was predicted conventional while being organic
- a parcel was predicted organic while being conventional
- a parcel was predicted correctly as conventional
- a parcel was predicted correctly as organic

It allows the user to reach conclusions on the compliance of the crop declaration. For example, the case where a parcel is predicted as organic while being conventional, is an indication of non-compliance of the declaration with the prediction of the classification models, which would need to be further checked.

Plants cultivated under organic and conventional farming principles present bio-chemico-physical differences that can be detectable by satellite imagery, especially during the vegetative and reproductive growth stages. The Identification of organic farming practices service benefits from these differences to discriminate between organic and non-organic (conventional) crops. The logic behind the service is to identify distinct patterns characterizing the growth and evolution of organic and conventional crops during the growing season, through the use of high-resolution optical satellite images and the derivation of image features depicting the phenological status of the cultivated parcels. Machine learning classifiers (MLC) have been trained to understand the temporal and spectral signatures of conventional and organic crops. The Predictor Layers emerge from Sentinel-2 MSI multispectral bands and include.

- Vegetation indices - quality masked - Gap filled NDVI 6d step timeseries
- NDVI timeseries temporal derivatives
- GLCM Image Texture Features
- Crop Phenology features

To support the creation of classification predictor layers, the service relies on a cloud-based processing framework of EO data to derive vegetation indices and phenology features, that subsequently feeds them as input to a trained classification algorithm. Cloud processing is achieved by the exploitation of the Copernicus Data Information Access Services (DIAS) infrastructure, and specifically the CREODIAS platform. Specifically, Sentinel-2 Level-2A have been exploited. The Sentinel-2 Level-2A products are offered in most of the cases as Bottom of Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance images derived from the associated Level-1C products.

The provider of the Identification of organic farming practices service is AgroApps, and the outcome product addresses to the Serbian Certification Body (CB), which is the relevant authority. The service has been integrated and delivered as an earth observation component of the ENVISION platform with geographical coverage across the Serbia region.

2.4.2 Brief description of the data product

The methodology process flow for the creation of the features that has been used for organic practice identification consisted of the successive preliminary steps of Vegetation Feature extraction and Ground truth data sampling of the EO derived products, which resulted to the creation of the training -validation dataset, and the resultant application of a machine learning framework for the creation of crop specific models. The framework approach was implemented on the CREODIAS platform environment with the aid of the following software and libraries:

- ESA SNAP Graph Processing Toolbox
- SAGA GIS
- Orfeo Toolbox and PhenOTB remote module
- R Libraries: mlr, caret, tidyverse, raster, sp, rgdal, tiff, ggplot2, maptools, zoo, signal, timeSeries, doParallel, dplyr
- Python libraries: rasterio, numpy, pandas, seaborn, matplotlib, imblearn, scikit-learn, xgboost

The general methodological framework for the training of ML models for organic practice identification is presented below:

- Field Data Import: LPIS+GSAA data subset import to the database
- Spatial Data POSTGIS processing + Descriptive Stats
- EO Data Import: Data import from CreoDIAS and Copernicus Dataspace APIs
- SoilGrids Import
- EO Feature Engineering: Vegetation and Image Texture indice timeseries and derivatives
- Data Outlier/Anomaly Detection

For prediction of the classification layer, it was considered to use the most accurate of the models trained in the past, with the use of historical datasets.

The data product was validated in terms of its accuracy relative to ground truth data from the LPIS and the GSAA that are considered the standard, against which the product is compared. Ground truth data kept out of the algorithm training and are considered as “unseen” by the model. Normally they are partitioned out of the input dataset, as a test set, in order to give an unbiased evaluation of the model predictive qualities. For reasons already mentioned in the previous chapter, that relate to the quantity of the pilot dataset, data from 2022 and 2023 seasons were used to validate those historical data models which showed superior accuracy. Accuracy evaluation was conducted with these datasets as “unseen”, firstly on a pixel level, and subsequently the traffic light system was evaluated on a parcel level. Confusion matrix notation and terminology was used for this aim. In the problem of statistical classification, a confusion matrix, also known as error matrix is a specific table layout that allows visualisation of the performance of an algorithm, typically a supervised learning one. Each row of the matrix represents the instances in an actual class while each column represents the instances in a predicted class, or vice versa – both variants are found in the literature. The name stems from the fact that it makes it easy to see whether the system is confusing two classes.

To assess the accuracy of our classification scheme, the following metrics were acquired:

- Overall Accuracy
- Precision: Precision (also called positive predictive value) is the fraction of relevant instances among the retrieved instances
- Recall: (true positive rate) is the probability of a positive test result, conditioned on the individual truly being positive.

- Specificity: (true negative rate) is the probability of a negative test result, conditioned on the individual truly being negative
- Balanced Accuracy: The balanced accuracy in binary and multiclass classification problems to deal with imbalanced datasets. It is defined as the average of recall obtained in each class.
- F1 Score: also known as balanced F-score or F-measure. The F1 score can be interpreted as a harmonic mean of the precision and recall

2.4.3 Dependencies of the service from other services

The technological implementation of the satellite-based Identification of organic farming practices service needs to find a compromise between the following elements:

1. availability of input data, with minimal contribution from end-users;
2. elaboration and processing time, with minimum possible timelag between E.O. data acquisition date and information delivery to final users;

2.4.3.1 Internal dependencies

1. System/server crash
2. Maintenance and time for the re-initialization or re-instating of the service at different servers

2.4.3.2 External dependencies/ Data Acquisition plan

1. Crop data.
 - The CBs must upload shp file of farm area, or can draw the farm area on the base map, or can provide coordinates of the farm in the reference World Geodetic System (WGS84). The farm must be considered to comply with organic farming practices and will be monitored throughout the growing season to verify its eligibility and compliance;
 - The external user must specify crop type;
 - The external user must specify sowing date;
2. Spectral data. The service can either acquire Sentinel-2 or Sentinel-1, or both, satellite images from any available service provider. Based on the imagery used, the appropriate bands and products will be assimilated for the calculation of the indices that will feed the ML classifier, the results will be crop specific, notifications will be produced based on the decisions of the object-based (parcel) analysis, and visualization (graphs, reports, widgets) will be populated based on the results.

2.4.4 Literature on the service/ product

The logic of organic crop identification relies on the fact that plants grown under organic farming principles tend to be less robust due to organic crop management techniques that apply less fertilizer and pesticide, do not use growth regulators and their sowing density is often smaller. The machine learning model will use EO derived features such as vegetation indices, biophysical parameters, SAR backscatter, GLCM textural indices, Phenology metrics, as predictor variables to discriminate between organic and non-organic practices. To this aim, spectral indicators related to the plants spectral signatures will be fully exploited in the multi-temporal training datasets, to calculate the phenological metrics that will enable accurate discrimination. Zonal Statistics of the EO indicators per parcel will

form the multi-temporal training datasets to feed the ML classifiers. SVM or Random Forest classifiers will be investigated in their accuracy to provide accurate results and form the final models to be incorporated in the platform.

2.4.5 Input data

The input data required are:

- Land Parcel Identification System: LPIS (Geosrbija) with data format: SQL table, shapefile, Geojson
- Farming Practice Declarations: GSAA (OCS) with data format: SQL table, csv
- Soil organic carbon/ Sand/ Silt/ Clay content: SoilGrids with data format: raster grids (.tif)
- VIS-NIR-SWIR reflectance: Sentinel-2 MSI with data format: raster grids (.SAFE)
- LC1
- L2A

2.4.6 Output data

The results of classification are provided in the data product as a vector geospatial feature which is served through the ENVISION platform, or alternatively could be served via WFS to the user, in a shapefile format. It contains the parcel polygon boundary geometries, and as far as attributes, the evaluation of the Classification as Organic/Conventional farming practice, in the representation of a traffic light system. Its values are given in a standardised confusion matrix terminology, and depict the result of the prediction in regards with what was initially declared. The prediction is decided by a configured threshold value on the classification probability, which is the actual output of the algorithm. If the spatial average within the parcel bounds is higher than 0.5 the parcel is inferred as organic. The traffic light values are the following :

- False Negative (FN) also known as type II underestimation error if a parcel was predicted conventional while being organic
- False Positive (FP) also known as type I overestimation error if a parcel was predicted organic while being conventional
- True Negative (TN) if a parcel was predicted correctly as conventional
- True Positive (TP) if a parcel was predicted correctly as organic

2.5 Soil Organic Carbon monitoring

2.5.1 Name of the service – provider

The Flemish business case focuses on deploying ENVISION service for topsoil Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring in Flanders, Belgium. The state of agricultural soils is checked by performing soil samplings and conducting laboratory examinations. However, these methods do not provide a continuous overview of the soil's state and require significant effort, time, and resources to be committed. Consequently, these types of controls have to be significantly reduced and replaced with a more automated process. The business case is implemented in Belgium, within the Flemish region, involving LV, the Flemish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries and Paying Agency, which is in Flanders' the official PA in charge of the financial support for agriculture and the implementation of CAP. The

Department of Agriculture and Fisheries is the Flemish Paying Agency and, together with the minister, outlines the policy on agriculture, horticulture, sea fishing and the countryside.

EV ILVO is responsible for the following:

- a) To perform the soil campaign together with LV.
- b) Design and develop a process that delivers SOC products to the Envision platform.
- c) to assess in which way and under which conditions those products can support the provision of CAP monitoring services.

2.5.2 Description of the service

The availability of a consistent number of ancillary data (or covariates) allows applying sampling strategies according to the feature space and not only based on the geographical space. Provided that the covariates are strongly related to the target variable, i.e., to the soil organic carbon (SOC), the sampling strategy based on feature space can ensure to collection soil samples representative of the whole range of SOC values within the investigated area. For these purposes, remote sensing data cheaply provides covariates over large areas. The physical link between spectral data in the optical domain and SOC exists and is widely exploited in remote sensing contexts. Thus, the absorbance/reflectance values at a given wavelength can be considered as covariates related to the target variable and consequently, the spectral variability can be exploited for sampling strategies based on feature space. However, some absorption features are quite broad and they can partly overlap with spectral regions related to a different soil property. For this reason, it is desirable using the whole spectrum as covariates instead of a single band or a narrow region. SOC prediction models exploit most of the spectral regions across the electromagnetic spectrum between 400 and 2500 nm and this is due to the large heterogeneity of the components of the organic matter.

In the ENVISION project, we used a soil sampling strategy based on a stratified feature-based approach, in which the feature space consists of the satellite spectral data retrieved by a multi-temporal analysis of the Sentinel-2 (S2) data and the strata are the soil associations of the Soil map of the Flemish region that assure an adequate geographical distribution and a proportioned representation of the all-soil types insisting in the Flemish region.

Prior to analysis, the soil samples were oven-dried at 40°C for 7 days, ground in a mortar and passed through a 250 µm sieve. Soil organic carbon (SOC) and Total N were measured by dry combustion using a Skalar Primacs SNC-1002. The soil organic carbon content (SOC) of the soil samples is displayed in the scatter plot below. The SOC in the dataset ranged from 0.29% till 12.40%. 88% of the samples contained a SOC content between 0,5 and 2,0 %.

Lab results are processed based on provided Excel files. To load in the in datapoints in the notebook Colab environment and Google Earth engine, sometimes a csv of the file was used, sometimes a shape file was created based on the coordinates in the Excel, projected to the WGS 84 coordinate system.

For the study area, we use a set of available data products like the World Cover map or the Soil Association Map of Flanders or the soil texture map of Flanders. Those data products are available for direct use either to support the identification of crop areas or the assignment of soil parameters to each pixel area or for the development of the Soil Quality Indicators. Since our methodology is EO-based and we target for large-scale coverage at EU level, we prefer to use data products that are harmonized and available in digital formats or, even better in web services or STAC catalogues. The

also aim for a min processing effort, which can be done again in an automated way using gdal python scripts or if that is not possible in a QGIS environment.

World Cover Soil map is extracted from Google Earth Engine. The format that is used there is the Cloud Optimised GeoTiff.

2.5.3 Dependencies of the service from other services

The SOC services need as an input the following data:

- SOC Carbon images (Maps) presenting topsoil soc values at high spatial resolution (10-30 meters).
- LPIS data.
- Administration boundaries.

2.5.3.1 External dependencies/ Data Acquisition plan

The following dependencies exist:

1. Data coming from SOC map provider. The SOC map providers need to deliver georeferenced images (with EPGS of 3857) that represent the SOC qualitative values at pixel size. For the needs of the Flemish SOC business use case, the development of the SOC images for the Flemish region will be done by ILVO. The methodology that EV ILVO is going to follow for the development of the SOC images for the Flemish region.
2. Vector LPIS data represent agricultural parcels for subsidy periods. The data need at least to contain the geometry and the crop type description, at a higher level. Crop types can be used to aggregate SOC results. For most EU countries those data are open.
3. Administration boundaries. Those are vector data that present the boundaries of administration regions. Merging of low-level boundaries may result in higher-level boundaries.

All vector data needs to follow specific geometry quality standards.

2.5.4 Input data

The input data are presented in the deliverable D3.5.

2.5.5 Output data

The output data are presented in the deliverable D3.5.

3 ENVISION's Development Pipeline

At the heart of ENVISION lied its stakeholders. The platform isn't just a technological development; it's an ecosystem where various entities coexist, collaborate, and converge to a common goal. The development team, alongside with the WP2 leader, recognised the need to deeply engage with these stakeholders.

As primary users, Paying Agencies' input was valuable. Requirements gathering from PAs focused on understanding their daily challenges in land monitoring as well as the bureaucratic and compliance challenges they face.

With a plethora of potential functionalities, the team had to prioritize. The scope was defined not just by the technological feasibility but primarily by the real-world impact. Key areas that were underlined included:

- User requirements: Ease of use was paramount. The platform had to be intuitive, responsive, and accessible. Moreover, it had to cater to users with varying degrees of tech-readiness.
- EO Data Integration: The platform's primary value proposition lies in leveraging EO data. The requirements here revolved around the frequency of data updates, the breadth of data (covering various geographical), and the depth (different soil layers and parameters).
- Machine Learning Functionalities: Given the vastness of EO data, manual analysis is near impossible. Machine learning's role was to sift through this data, identify patterns, and provide actionable insights. Requirements here involved defining algorithms, training data sets, and validation processes.
- Insight tools: Ultimately, the data and insights need presentation. The platform had to offer robust tools that could generate comprehensive yet easy-to-understand insights. These insights would aid PAs in decision-making.

Requirements gathering for ENVISION wasn't just a step; it was a foundation. By grounding the platform in the real needs of its users, the team set a clear path forward. The meticulousness of this phase ensured that the subsequent development was aligned with the genuine challenges and aspirations of the agricultural community.

In the context of ENVISION, the design and architecture phase were paramount in ensuring the platform holistic functionality and performance. The overarching goal was to devise a platform that not only was technologically advanced but also user-centric, ensuring a fine balance between sophisticated Earth Observation (EO) capabilities and usability.

The design and architecture phase of ENVISION was not just about building a technically advanced platform. It was about understanding the diverse user base's distinct needs and crafting a system that, while being at the forefront of EO technology, remained accessible, intuitive, and beneficial to all its users.

Adopting the Agile Scrum methodology, the platform's development was divided into manageable sprints, usually spanning 2-4 weeks. A prioritized list of features and functionalities formed the product backlog. During each sprint, specific features were selected for development. This approach ensured that there was continuous integration of components and that feedback was constantly incorporated, making the development process dynamic and responsive.

Adhering to the best coding practices ensured that the platform is modular and can scale according to needs. The team integrated various components like EO data processing tools, machine learning algorithms, and other functionalities. Proper version control, documentation, and adherence to coding standards ensured that the codebase remains consistent and maintainable.

A robust testing methodology ensured that the platform is free from bugs and meets user expectations. Unit Testing focused on individual components, validating that each function or module works as intended. Integration Testing came next, ensuring that these individual components interact without issues. System Testing evaluated the entire system in an environment mimicking the production setting. Finally, User Acceptance Testing (UAT) brought in actual users to test the platform, verifying that the platform aligns with their needs and expectations.

Even after deployment, the development process wasn't truly end. Gathering feedback from users and stakeholders provided insights into areas of improvement.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable aims to provide the ENVISION system's architecture and the services specifications in detail, the technologies stack and development processes that have been followed for the development of the ENVISION system.

This document's target audience is mainly the technical partners of the consortium so that we all have a common understanding of ENVISION's architecture. It will act as a reference and a source of information for all partners.

End of Document

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